

Research

Disability as Diversity: Hiring Behaviors of Human Resource Specialist

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Abstract: *People with disabilities can be an effective human resource for the country regardless of their disabilities. However, due to the negative stereotypes associated with their performance they lack job opportunities. This quantitative study investigates the effects of features of diversity climate, subjective norms of industry, hiring intentions, attitudes and perceived behavioral control on actual hiring behaviors of managers and human resource specialist for people with disabilities in industrial sector of Karachi. A sample of 200 managers and human resource specialist from business/finance, education, retail and sales industry in Karachi has been selected for the study. The data about their hiring behaviors, effects of features of diversity climate, subjective norms of industry, hiring intentions, attitudes and perceived behavioral control was gathered on a questionnaire adapted from Araten-Bergman (2016). The results revealed that subjective norms of the industries, hiring intentions and attitudes towards PWDs significantly influence actual hiring behaviors of the managers and human resource specialist. However perceived behavioral control and features of diversity climate doesn't have any direct influence on hiring behaviors. The study indicates a strong need for changing negative stereotypes related to people with disabilities.*

Keywords: *Disability, Diversity, Hiring Intentions, Hiring Behaviors, Human Resource Management*

Introduction

People with Disabilities (PWDs) are the world largest minority group and almost 15% of the world population has any kind of disability (Khan, Korac-Kakabadse, Skouloudis, & Dimopoulos, 2019). The term disability is characterized by functional limitations due to physical, intellectual, sensory impairment or any other medical condition (Caballero, 2019).

Negative stereotypes about the employees with disabilities are common across the world. PWDs are most vulnerable group for discrimination, unemployment and unfair treatment at workplace (Tuan, Rowley, Khai, Qian, Masli, & Le, 2020).

Research indicates that there is a lack of social preparation, as well as numerous functional and architectural barriers for PWDs at workplace. Prejudice around their ability to contribute in the business context is one of the biggest obstacles to social inclusion of PWDs in industry. Prejudices are based on generalized beliefs about personal characteristics (attributes) of minority groups, which are considered to be typically negative (Friedman, 2020). Currently, in Pakistan there are is a dearth of research that identifies the difficulties of people with disabilities to enter the industry and the work management of PWDs who are already inserted in the industry (Arsh, Darain, Zeb, Ullah, Ullah & Ilyas, 2019).

Considering the prejudice for PWDs hiring behaviors of managers in relation to the work possibilities of the PWDs and the difficulties in their job placement, the objective of the present research was to verify if there are relations between the hiring behaviors for PWDs to how PWDs are seen by managers and human resource specialist. The study also attempts to find out the subjective norms of the organization, features of diversity management practices and perceived behavioral control on actual hiring behaviors of the managers.

Literature Review

Disability has been viewed in a different ways throughout history and that these ways of perception had an impact on the relationship of society with people with deficiency. Carvalho-Freitas and Marques (2010) defined the factors that denominate conceptions of disabilities such as: modes of thought built along the history and which are used for qualification of people with disabilities, in addition to offering justifications for related actions.

For the construction of the conceptions of disability throughout history, four matrices of interpretation were identified (Mays, 2020). According to Carvalho-Freitas and Marques (2010) these matrices are modalities are anchored in conceptions of individual world and society that organize the social activity, recognize and qualify needs, and admit ways to satisfy them. Conceptions are ways of disability interpretation prevalent over time and that are characterized as matrices that shaped and legitimized the distinction of people with disabilities, both in society as at work.

Carvalho-Freitas and Marques (2007) identified six disability interpretation matrices over time. However, two of them were not operationalized by Carvalho-Freitas (2007) for use in empirical research related to work situations. The matrices identified and operationalized by Carvalho-Freitas (2007) and which reflect the conceptions of disability in work situations are four.

The first conception, the spiritual conception matrix of the disability, starts from the assumption that religious beliefs influence the way of assessing disability and the possibilities of people with disabilities. Those who share this thought recognize and qualify disability as a manifestation of divine desires or punishments and usually develop actions at work, based on compassion towards people with disabilities, in addition to having greater difficulties in evaluating their performance, as they feel hurting the principle of charity, as identified in an empirical research conducted by Carvalho-Freitas (2009). However, the recognition of the influence of religious beliefs on people's choices regarding work is not new, as can be seen in Weber (1989).

The second conception, *normality as an interpretation matrix*, is based on the premise that the standards of normality defined by medical knowledge work as a means of assessing disability and the possibilities of people with disabilities. It is a matrix in which the predominant thought is characterized by the qualification of the disability as a *deviation from normality* or *illness*, which contributes to the segregation of people with disabilities at work. As the deviant is seen at a disadvantage in relation to the others, when PWDs are inserted in the world of work, those who classify the disability from this perspective tend to assign specific functions to them, based on the type of disability (and not the potentialities) PWDs. Thus, they tend to assign them to activities of lesser *status* or little or no possibility of growth and career, because the underlying belief is that they are not capable, since they are not classified as normal people.

The third conception, *inclusion as an interpretation matrix*, has a socio-political perspective and sees disability as a problem for society; a problem generated by the lack of equal conditions for the full exercise of work by people with disabilities. It encourages the development of actions to adapt conditions, practices and instruments aimed at creating a work environment accessible to all. It also contributes to the rescue of the dimension of citizenship of the person with a disability, insofar as it focuses on disability as a social, historical, geographical

and economically situated issue. The rights and duties of these people are limited to a certain time, space and culture. In the last instance, inclusion is seen as a set of actions by society and organizations to offer conditions for the full exercise of citizenship and the development of the professional potential of people with disabilities (PWDs), seeking: the development of autonomous work by these people, the access to information, job security, possibility of development, social integration, participation in decisions, organizational belonging, etc.

Other authors who discuss disability from a socio-political perspective are Lambert (2019), Nwalutu (2019), Onazi (2020) and Ståhl, Costa-Black & Loisel (2018) which discusses the development of autonomous work by these people, access to information, job security, the possibility of development, social integration, participation in decisions, organizational belonging, etc.

The fourth conception, *matrix of technical interpretation of the disability*, assumes that when the disability is seen as a resource to be managed within organizations, it starts to be considered in its dimensions of functionality for work. New aspects of the disability are considered, constituting an instrumental perspective of assessing the disability, taking into account the ability to perform roles in the organization, benefits arising from the hiring of people with disabilities, the PWD's link with the organization and need training. Thus, the technical matrix is reflected in four factors:

- *Perception of PWDs performance*: indicates the possibilities of functional performance of activities attributed to PWDs in organizations. Research shows that most organizations value competitiveness, and PWDs tend to be seen as unable to compete on the same *performance* standards; that bureaucratic organizations have as a criterion of equity to give the same conditions to all workers, not reacting positively to the request to adapt working conditions for PWDs; and that organizations normally expect workers to develop their work autonomously and that PWDs are considered more dependent. The performance of people with disabilities is a relevant criterion for analysis in organizational environments, whether in terms of quality, productivity, general performance of activities, or in the competitiveness of the company, aiming to configure a predominant way of assessing this dimension of the ways of seeing disability in the work environment.

- *Perception of the link that the PWD maintains with the organization:* it focuses on the commitment assumed, or not, by the PWDs in relation to its work and in relation to the organization that hired it.
- *Perception of the benefits of hiring a PWD:* focuses on the possible gains, or losses, arising from the hiring of PWDs, both for the internal climate and for the internal or external image of the organization.
- *Perception of the need for training:* vision on the part of managers and co-workers, in order to facilitate the process of insertion and socialization of people with disabilities.

For Leshota and Sefotho (2020), people's perception is subject to various distortions, that is, people can see others in a different way different from what they are, and an example of this is the stereotyping that is understood as: the process of using an impression standardized group of people to influence our impression of an individual in particular. It is a way of form consistent impressions about other people, assuming that everyone has certain common characteristics by virtue of affiliation (both assigned obtained) to a group such as category, such as race, gender, profession or social class.

There are three basic aspects of stereotyping. The first is identify some category of people; the second is to assume that people belonging to that category have certain features and behaviors; and the third is to form a general opinion that everyone belonging to that category have the same traits and behaviors. Thus, beliefs about people are created based on a particular group rather than looking at uniqueness of each person. To author, when the characteristic of a person or group covers all other characteristics of the person is called the halo effect. That characteristic that is highlighted can be positive or negative, thus creating form a general impression that would be correspondingly both good and bad (McLean, Hardie, Paul, A., Paul, G., Savage, Shields & Harden, 2017).

Theoretical Background

McGregor (1999) developed the argument that basic beliefs that administrators have about the people and the nature of human behavior influence managers in the way they motivate and manage the work of their subordinates. McGregor (1999) developed the Theory X and Theory Y which are extreme images about beliefs of managers. Those who have basic assumption the beliefs of Theory X tend to think that people need to be controlled, coerced and

punished so that strive and achieve the goals organizational. They also believe that the human being, in a way general, has little ambition, either guarantee of things, prefers to escape responsibilities and be directed.

In contrast, managers that orient themselves, assuming basic beliefs typified in Theory Y, tend to agree that, for nature, the common human being hates work, because depending on conditions, work can be as much source of satisfaction as well as punishment. For managers who share this assumption, the human being is always willing to self-control and the self-directed towards the goals with which he commits himself. Beyond addition, they are naturally active people, who seek satisfaction at work, who get tired of monotonous routines and that they are, in general, creative. Theory Y assumes that nature's limitations within organizations, does not are human being's limits, but limits of the direction itself in discovering the performance of potential resources humans. Thus, when relating the conceptions of disability, of a hand, and the beliefs and perceptions that managers have about people and the nature of human behavior, on the other, it seeks to understand whether disability can be a generating factor so much impact that it interferes with manager's perception. This is, it is assumed that a manager anchored in the assumptions of Theory Y would also have a provision positive towards people with deficiency. Otherwise, the assumption would be that the disability is such an impacting factor that those same managers would have negative provisions in relation to disabled people.

Methodology

This study employed both descriptive and causal analyses. Frequency, percentages and mean score and regression analysis are utilized. Convenient sampling is used and questions are derived from the study of Araten-Bergman (2016). The five points Likert scale (1= Strongly Disagree and 5 = Strongly Agree) is used for item in the construct.

Information was collected at individual level. The respondents were located in Karachi. Survey questionnaires were distributed to 324 target respondents. A total of 200 complete questionnaires were utilized successfully. Target respondents are across different sectors of the industry including education, retail, financial/business and services sector.

This study seeks to test the following hypotheses:

- H₁ The features of diversity climate has no significant impact on hiring behaviors of managers and human resource specialist for PWDs in industrial sector of Karachi

- H₂ The subjective norms of industry has no significant impact on hiring behaviors of managers and human resource specialist for PWDs in industrial sector of Karachi
- H₃ The hiring intentions of managers/human resource specialist has no significant impact on hiring behaviors of managers and human resource specialist for PWDs in industrial sector of Karachi
- H₄ The attitudes of managers/human resource specialist has no significant impact on hiring behaviors of managers and human resource specialist for PWDs in industrial sector of Karachi
- H₅ The perceived behavioral control has no significant impact on hiring behaviors of managers and human resource specialist for PWDs in industrial sector of Karachi

Data Analysis and Results

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Respondents

Table 1 describes the demographics details of the respondents. The data from 200 managers and human resource specialist from financial, educational retail and service industry was obtained. 44.5% of the population were managers and human resource specialist from Financial/ Business industry of Karachi including Bank Islami, Muslim Commercial Bank and EFU Life Insurance. 60% of the sample comprised of managers and human resource specialist from retail industries of Karachi, including Imtiaz Super market and Chase value Centre. 9% of managers and human resource specialist were from Iqra University Karachi, Dewa Academy and NOWPDP. 33 % of the sample was from services sector of Karachi including K-Electric and Sui Gas. The population comprises from 36.5% of female and 63.5 of male population. The majority 67% of the study participants were Master’s degree holder from medium scale industries.

	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Gender		
Female	73	36.5
Male	127	63.5
Educational Level		

Bachelors	6	3.0
Masters	134	67.0
MPhil	26	13.0
Doctorate	34	17.0
Industry Type		
Financial/Business	89	44.5
Retail	60	30.0
Educational	18	9.0
Services	33	16.5
Organizational Size (number of employees)		
Very Small (up to 10)	20	10.0
Small (11-30)	43	21.5
Medium (31-100)	99	49.5
Large (over 101)	38	19.0
Sector		
Profit	176	88.0
Non Profit	24	12.0
Job Title		
Human Resource Specialist	162	81.0
CEO/President/Owner	38	19.0
Total	200	100

Table 2: Reliability Statistics

Internal consistency for the items in each construct of the questionnaire is represented in Table 2. The constructs include Hiring Intentions, Hiring Behaviour, Attitudes, Perceived Behavioural control, subjective norms and features of diversity climate. The researcher assessed the data for internal consistency at two stages including pilot test and final testing. During pilot testing of the items, item no 2 for construct attitudes was found insignificant due to which it was

deleted during the final testing stage. Table 3 indicates the item total statistic for construct attitudes.

	<i>Pilot Test</i>	<i>Final Test</i>		
	Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items	Deleted Items
Hiring Intentions	.709	.709	3	-
Hiring Behavior	.887	.887	5	-
Attitudes	.224	.661	6	3
Perceived Behavioral Control	.80	.8-		
Subjective Norms	.880	.880		
Features of Diversity Climate	.934	.934		

Table 3: Item-Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Deleted	Item Scale Variance Corrected if Item Deleted	Scale Variance Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Deleted
A2	14.51	9.896	.240	.358	.080
A3	12.57	10.359	.088	.272	.201
A4	14.32	10.614	.116	.183	.177
A5	12.45	11.112	.039	.289	.239
A6	12.58	12.032	-.061	.018	.315
A1	14.19	9.635	.173	.299	.121

Table 4 : KMO and Bartlett's Test

The value for alpha must be more than 0.50 for the reliability of the tool. Table 4 indicates that the value of KMO of independent variable is 0.736 which shows 73% of variance.

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.736
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity		2896.75
Approx. Chi-Square		1
df		300
Sig.		.000

Table 5: Component Matrix

Table 5 indicates construct validity for the instrument. The component matrix was obtained by rotated component matrix in SPSS software. Principal Component Analysis for the instrument indicates six extracted constructs which are valid for hypothesis testing.

Rotated Component Matrix

		Component					
		1	2	3	4	5	6
1	Features of diversity climate	.941					
2		.931					
3		.895					
4		.881					
5	Subjective norms		.896				
6			.884				
7			.856				
8			.781				
9	Hiring Intentions			.903			
10				.876			

11		.824
12		.858
13	Hiring Behavior	.798
14		.706
15		.835
16	Attitudes	.830
17		.622
18		.811
19		.770
10	Perceived Behavioral Control	.543

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

Table 6: Descriptive statistics for Respondents

Table 6 represents average scores for the construct of the instruments. The mean value of the construct “features of diversity climate” is 7.8500 having 5.21281. The mean score of the subjective norms is 8.8500 with 4.57956. The means for construct “hiring intentions” is 4.2300 with 2.76684. For construct “hiring behaviors” the mean score is 4.3900 with 2.401 of standard deviations. The construct “Attitude” have mean score of 5.3417 with 3.03745 of standard deviations. The mean score for “Perceived Behavioral Control” is 9.1050 with 2.81310 of standard deviations

Descriptive Statistics

N	Mini	Maxi	Mean	Std.	Skewness	Kurtosis
	mum	mum		Deviation		
Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic
					Std. Error	Std. Error

Features of diversity climate	200	3.00	19.00	7.850	5.21281	1.166	.172	-.326	.342
Subjective norms	200	4.00	19.00	8.850	4.57956	.633	.172	-	1.004
Hiring Intentions	200	3.00	15.00	4.230	2.76684	2.722	.172	6.623	.342
Hiring Behavior	200	3.00	15.00	4.390	3.13481	2.401	.172	4.731	.342
Attitude	199	3.00	15.00	5.341	3.03745	1.298	.172	.811	.343
Perceived Behavioral Control	200	3.00	14.00	9.105	2.81310	-.030	.172	-.427	.342
Valid N (listwise)	199								

Table 7: Regression Analysis

Regression analysis was obtained to test the hypothetical statements made by the researcher using SPSS package. Table 7 indicates the effect of independent variables on the dependent variables. The R-value obtained in the regression analysis indicates multiple correlation coefficients (.707), which depicts that the change in dependent variable (Hiring Behaviour) is caused by the change in independent variables features of diversity climate, subjective norms, hiring intentions, attitudes and perceived behavioural control. Moreover, the value for R^2 represents coefficient of determination (.599 = 59.3 percent), which is the variance proportion brought by the independent variable in dependent variable.

Model Summary

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error of
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1		Square	Square	the Estimate
1	.707 ^a	.599	.586	3.70588

a. Predictors: (Constant), HiringIn, At, PBC, SN, FDC

Table 8: ANOVA

Table 8 shows the fitness of the model to regress. The F ratio $F(5,192) = 38.269$, $p < .0005$ shows that model is good fit. The independent variables (features of diversity climate, subjective norms, hiring intentions, attitudes and perceived behavioural control) significantly predict the dependent variable (hiring behaviour). The regression equation that predicts the change in dependent variable caused by the independent variables is as follows:

$$\text{Hiring Behavior} = -1.527 + (.117 \times \text{Subjective Norms}) + (.144 \times \text{Attitudes}) + (.666 \times \text{Hiring Intentions})$$

Therefore, it can be said that variables subjective norms, attitudes and hiring intentions predicts hiring behavior of managers and human resource specialist, $p < .05$.

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	2627.859	5	525.572	38.269	.000 ^b
	2636.848	192	13.734		
	5264.707	197			

a. Dependent Variable: HB

b. Predictors: (Constant), HiringIn, At, PBC, SN, FDC

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized		Standardized	t	Sig.	
	Coefficients					
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
	(Constant	-1.527	1.622			
	)			-.941	.348	
	FDC	-.031	.052	-.031	-.601	.549
1	SN	.132	.058	.117	2.272	.024
	At	.204	.074	.144	2.773	.006
	PBC	-.027	.094	-.015	-.288	.774
	HiringIn	.759	.059	.666	12.803	.000

a. Dependent Variable: HB

Table 9: Summary of the Hypotheses

Table 9 displays that the study failed to reject the first and the last null hypothesis. The significant relationships were obtained between the independent variables subjective norms, hiring intentions and attitudes and dependent variable hiring behavior. However no relationship was obtained for features of diversity climate and perceived behavioral control on hiring behavior for people with disabilities in industrial sector of Karachi.

N	Hypotheses	Sig	Status
o.		Value	
H ¹	The features of diversity climate has no significant impact on hiring behaviors of managers and human resource specialist for PWDs in industrial sector of Karachi	.549	Failed to Reject
H ²	The subjective norms of industry has no significant impact on hiring behaviors of managers and human resource specialist for PWDs industrial sector of Karachi	.024	Rejected
H ³	The hiring intentions has no significant impact on hiring	.000	Rejected

	behaviors of managers and human resource specialist for PWDs in industrial sector of Karachi		
H ⁴	The attitudes of managers/human resource specialist has no significant impact on hiring behaviors of managers and human resource specialist for PWDs in industrial sector of Karachi	.006	Rejected
H ⁵	The perceived behavioural control has no significant impact on hiring behaviors of managers and human resource specialist for PWDs in industrial sector of Karachi	.774	Failed to Reject

Conclusion and Recommendations

The purpose of this study was to investigate the effects of features of diversity climate, subjective norms of industry, hiring intentions, attitudes and perceived behavioral control on actual hiring behaviors of managers and human resource specialist for people with disabilities in industrial sector of Karachi. The results indicate that subjective norms, hiring intentions and attitudes significantly effects hiring behavior for people with disabilities of managers and human resource specialist in the industries. However, a feature of diversity climate and perceived behavioral control does not have on any significant influence on actual hiring behavior of managers and human resource specialist in industries of Karachi. The results supports the findings of Araten-Bergman (2016) which states that attitudes, norms and hiring intentions significantly predicts the hiring behavior of inclusion and exclusion of people with disabilities.

Results of the study indicate that managers of the industries are biased about disabilities and they base their decisions on their own perception of the disability. They don't rely on concrete steps for exclusion or inclusion of PWDs. Most of the organizations doesn't have climate that support any type of disability or neither have they written policy or documentation of hiring of PWDs. The findings suggest a strong need to change organizational attitudes for disability in order to promote diverse hiring. As Tuan, Rowley, Khai, Qian, Masli & Le (2020) suggest that the negative stereotypes about people with disabilities in workplace such as expected lower productivity and risk of accidents doesn't influence the hiring rates but it can also influence the work lives of many employees with disabilities.

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Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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